

CLASSIFICATION OF TRANSLATION OF FIXED-WORD COMPOUND-TERMS

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Abstract: *This article is dedicated to the translation of fixed-word compound-terms usually does not cause special difficulties. In contrast to compound word terms, the grammatical form of terminological word compound components clearly represents the meaningful connections between Termin components.*

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The translation of fixed-word compound-terms usually does not cause special difficulties. In contrast to compound word terms, the grammatical form of terminological word compound components clearly represents the meaningful connections between Termin components. However, when translating stagnant verbal combinations, it should always be borne in mind that they are also a holistic, whole lexical unit in spiritual relationships, just like compound words. In this regard, the general meaning of fixed-word terminological compounds is not equal to the meaning of the individual components that make up the term.

The meaning of individual words in which a stationary terminological word is part of a compound, always to one degree or another, the whole word is subject to the spiritual composition of the compound. Therefore, of particular importance in the theory and practice of translation is the issue of how much a stationary terminological word (lexeme, component) quoted retains its spiritual independence in the composition of a compound.

A stationary terminological word can be divided into three main groups according to the degree of re-comprehension of the components of the compound, the acquisition of meaning and meaning:

- 1) word compounds whose all components retain their proper (original) lexical meanings;
- 2) a word whose components are one or all re-understood, but whose meanings can be deduced from the meanings of the components compounds;
- 3) a word whose components cannot extract meaning from the meanings of compounds.

Moreover the components retain their original (tag) lexical meanings, as well as the verbal compounds, which are slightly different in their own sense integrity, integrity, and are made according to the degree of proximity to the free combination of words, should not be overlooked.

Syntactically, the preposition of can be designed in the form of a structure, for example, a wing spar is a wing spar, cabin depressurization is a violation of the tightness of the cabin (air, water, sound become passable) and the like. Determinant affiliation determinant stable terminological phrases expressing an attitude in a broad sense are much closer to free phrases. Each component of such vocabulary performs the same spiritual function. Unlike other types of defining dictionaries, each component of this type of vocabulary can have a separate determinant, in addition, a more stable vocabulary will not suffer: longeron of the star wing, main longeron of the wing, depressurization of the passenger cabin, partial depressurization of the cabin.

This is exactly the situation observed in Russian and Uzbek: the right wing spar is the right wing spar, the main wing spar is the main wing spar, passenger cabin depressurization is a violation of the tightness of the passenger compartment, partial cabin depressurization is a partial violation of the tightness of the compartment, etc.

However, despite the relative spiritual independence of the components of this type of vocabulary, such dictionaries are distinguished by greater spiritual integrity compared to a free combination of words similar to them, let's compare: spar of the wing and be a free combination of words – room of the father or be a free combination of words – a friend's book and a stable word compilation-A book of complaints and suggestions.

Sometimes this type is supported by the integrity of stable word combinations-terms, as well as a slight change in the subject itself, denoting the phrase, in relation to the subject, denoting only the word identified with it (the main component of the phrase). For example, the chassis of a lift – the "chassis lift" is not just a lift (i.e., a "device for moving a person and cargo in an upright position") mounted on the chassis of an aircraft, but a special device designed for lifting and lowering the chassis, characterized by a number of fundamental design features. Lift chassis-the term "chassis lift" can serve as a good example of the separation of the terminological meaning from the dictionary.

A number of stable determinative phrases differ in that their main component has a much more general meaning. He only gives instructions as to which category the current concept belongs to; while the main spiritual task is assigned to the determinant, which represents the exact nature of the concept.

Thus, it can be concluded that the words (components) that make up the aforementioned consonants are clarified in terms of terminating without being understood.

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